

Ammonium recovery from pig slurry storage pits using modular submerged microbial electrolysis cells

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The open-air farm's storage of livestock manure poses a significant challenge due to emissions of greenhouse gases and ammonia into the atmosphere. Bioelectrochemical systems have been widely studied for ammonium recovery from wastewater [1], prompting this project to explore the application of a submerged Microbial Electrolysis Cell (MEC) within livestock manure storage pits to mitigate ammonia emissions. The objective of this study is to design, construct, and operate a new configuration MEC that can be submerged in a livestock manure storage pit to recover ammonium. Furthermore, the potential impact of ammonium extraction and recovery by the MEC on atmospheric emissions from slurry storage pits will be assessed.

A tubular submerged MEC has been developed, comprising a NAFION™ membrane bag housing the cathode compartment (1.2 L) internally. Carbon felt wraps around the membrane exterior as the anode. A modular design with 4 MEC units has been constructed and submerged in an outdoor tank with 600 L of raw pig slurry. The cathode compartments have been filled with a NaCl solution (0.1 g/L) which is continuously recirculated with a peristaltic pump. The MECs' electrodes are connected in parallel with a power source. A second tank, without MEC, is used as control.

During the first 68 days of operation of the submerged module, 25 g of N have been recovered in the catholyte, representing an average of 1.12 gN/m²/d. From day 67, a second module has been submerged in the tank, to increase ammonia recovery and evaluate the influence of ammonium reduction on pig slurry ammonia emissions into the atmosphere, currently in progress.

The new design of modular submerged MEC is an initial step towards the upscaling of this technology for the application in the recovery of ammonium from outdoor storage of livestock manure and the reduction of emissions into the atmosphere. The recovered ammonia solution can be reused as fertilizer in order to close the nutrient cycle.

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References

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